

Superradially expanding flux tubes of young stars' coronae

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Abstract

We discuss the reasons for extremely high wind speed observed in 3D MHD simulations of fast rotating young stars with intense magnetic fields. We find that superradially expanding flux tubes in latitude and in longitude are responsible for a significant acceleration in our simulations. We extend here the analysis presented in Réville *et al.* (2016) thanks to an analytical model introduced by Kopp & Holzer (1976). We find that the expansion factor observed in the simulations is coherent with the fastest speeds we observe. This phenomena needs to be accounted for to model speed distribution of young stars' winds.

1 Introduction

The structure of solar-like stars winds are still poorly understood. A growing sample of astrosphere detection in the Ly α absorption spectrum (Wood, 2004; Wood *et al.*, 2014) has brought constraints on the evolution on the total mass loss evolution as a function of the X-ray emission. Yet, these observations only provide signatures of integrated properties and the structure of the coronal magnetic fields and wind speed is as of today only reachable through simulation. Our study, exhaustively discussed in Réville *et al.* (2016), is made of a set of six MHD wind simulations of stars of different ages. The surface magnetic fields of those stars are constrained by spectropolarimetric measurements (Folsom *et al.*, 2016). The simulations yield the magnetic and velocity fields as well as the temperature and density of the wind at each point of the simulation domain obtain self-consistently with the imposed value of the magnetic field at the boundary (see Vidotto *et al.*, 2014; do Nascimento *et al.*, 2016; Alvarado-Gómez *et al.*, 2016; Nicholson *et al.*, 2016, for similar studies).

We find in our study that the speed distribution of the young and fast rotating stars of our sample follow a trimodal distribution that can be explain thanks to the interaction with the intense magnetic field. The magneto-centrifugal effect as well as a superradial expansion of the magnetic field in the wind solutions create a fast wind which can only appear in rapidly rotating stars. Here, we deepen the analysis made on the superradial expansion of flux tube in Réville *et al.* (2016) thanks to a semi-analytical model introduced by Kopp & Holzer (1976).

2 Model Description

Our model uses spectropolarimetric maps of the surface magnetic field of six solar-like stars: HII 296, BD- 16351, TYC 5164-567-1, DX Leo, AV 2177 and the Sun in 1996 (Folsom *et al.*, 2016; Réville *et al.*, 2016). These maps constrain the surface magnetic field of the star that is considered as a boundary condition in our setup. We solve the ideal MHD equations in a rotating frame using the PLUTO code (Mignone *et al.*, 2007) to obtain a steady-state structure of the coronal

properties for each star: the magnetic and velocity fields, the mass density and the thermal pressure. We use a cartesian geometry and the domain is a box of $60R_\star^3$ centered on the star. The coronal heating that is thought to drive the solar wind is modeled thanks to an ideal gas equation of state with an adiabatic index $\gamma = 1.05$ for all the stars.

To account for the evolution of stellar coronae with age, we change the coronal base temperature and density of each case using a power law dependance of these parameters to the rotation rate Ω_\star . The sample contains very young stars whose rotation rate vary up to $10.7\Omega_\odot$ (see Réville *et al.*, 2016, for a precise description of the sample). The exponents of these power laws are chosen following the work of Ivanova & Taam (2003) and Holzwarth & Jardine (2007) such as:

$$T = T_\odot \left(\frac{\Omega_\star}{\Omega_\odot} \right)^{0.1}, \quad n = n_\odot \left(\frac{\Omega_\star}{\Omega_\odot} \right)^{0.6}. \quad (1)$$

The coronal temperature and density are calibrated to obtain a value of the solar angular momentum loss of $3.0 \times 10^{-14} M_\odot/\text{yr}$ at the solar rotation rate and a wind speed of around 450 km/s at 1 AU. This gives $T_\odot = 1.5 \times 10^6 \text{K}$ and $n_\odot = 10^8 \text{cm}^{-3}$. We will focus here on two ~ 120 Myr old stars of our sample: HII 296 ($\Omega_\star = 10.7\Omega_\odot$) and TYC 5164-567-1 ($\Omega_\star = 5.4\Omega_\odot$).

3 Results

One of the striking result of this study is the trimodal form of the speed distribution observed in the fastest rotators of our sample. In Figure 1, we show the speed distribution of HII 296 and TYC 5164-567-1 at 25 stellar radii. The three peaks of the distribution can be clearly seen with a first component around 250 km/s, a second component between 350–400 km/s and the fastest component with speeds above 500 km/s. The spatial distribution of these distributions is also illustrated through a volume rendering of the Mach number $M = v/\sqrt{\gamma p/\rho}$ in 3D.

It is clear that the slow component (in blue in the vol-

Figure 1: On the left panel, the speed distribution for two stars of sample. On the right, a volume rendering of the Mach number obtained in those simulations showing the spatial structure of the trimodal distribution of wind speed for rapidly rotating young stars.

ume rendering) appears near the streamers -or dead zones- where magnetic tension confines the coronal plasma. The slow component goes on beyond the closed loops following the current sheet similarly to what is observed in the solar system (McComas *et al.*, 2008). The intermediate component (in green) is coming from coronal holes mostly located above the pole. The black, dashed line in Figure 1 represent the wind speed obtained at this radius for a spherically symmetric polytropic wind model at the base coronal temperature used in the simulation. We can see that this value matches the intermediate component observed in the speed distributions, given that this is the speed one would expect without interaction with the magnetic field.

The third component involves more ingredients. First, magneto-centrifugal acceleration (Weber & Davis, 1967; Michel, 1969; Sakurai, 1985; Washimi & Shibata, 1993) is responsible for part of the acceleration observed in the third peak of the trimodal distribution (see Figure 1). The theoretical speed amplitude obtained by a simplified Weber and Davis model (see also Sakurai, 1985; Réville *et al.*, 2015b) is marked with the dashed, magenta line. In the case of HII 296, this magneto-centrifugal acceleration accounts well for

the mean amplitude of the peak. However, the tail of the distribution goes on to much higher speeds.

In the case of TYC 5164-567-1, the Weber and Davis model does not match the fast wind component of the speed distribution. Hence, other processes must be invoked to explain the high speed observed in the simulations. A closer look at the volume rendering of the Mach number in Figure 1 reveals that part of the fast wind is located within flux tubes that expand above the equator. Expansion of flux tubes plays a fundamental role in the speed of the outflow.

In the solar wind, the observed speed at 1 AU has been shown to be anti-correlated to the expansion factor f_{exp} (Wang & Sheeley, 1990), which quantifies how much a given flux tube expands compared to the ideal radial expansion obtained for a split-monopole topology of the magnetic field. This parameter is defined by:

$$f_{\text{exp}} = \frac{A_2}{A_1} \left(\frac{r_1}{r_2} \right)^2, \quad (2)$$

where A_i are the area of the section of the flux tube located at the spherical radius r_i . The observed anti-correlation is

Figure 2: Sketch of the superradial expansion of flux tubes. On the left panel, the collimation of field lines towards the axis due to high rotation is responsible for a latitudinal superradial expansion. On the right, the magnetic flux gradient at the stellar surface will generate a differential magnetic stress on both end of the flux tube and create a longitudinal superradial expansion.

probably due to a superradial expansion of the flux tube inside the sonic surface, where the wind is subsonic (Wang & Sheeley, 1991). In our simulations of young stars, the expansion occurs beyond the sonic surface and two different phenomena are creating a latitudinal and a longitudinal expansion. First, at high rotation, the Lorentz force created by the azimuthal magnetic field component is directed toward the rotation axis, creating a collimation effect (see e.g. Ustyugova *et al.*, 1999; Ferreira, 2013; Réville *et al.*, 2015a). Near the dead zones, the field lines are bended downward to follow the structure of the streamer. This creates the latitudinal superradial expansion and is clearly visible in Figure 1. A sketch of this configuration is shown in Figure 2, on the left panel.

Second, we observe in the simulation a longitudinal superradial expansion that is due to flux concentration at the stellar surface. The strong gradient of magnetic flux creates a differential stress on the magnetic field lines that are thus more or less efficiently set in rotation with the star. This process is illustrated in the right panel of Figure 2. This process creates an expansion of the same order than the latitudinal expansion in the fast flux tubes we observe in our simulations.

In Figure 3 we show a cut in the (y, z) plane of our wind solution for TYC 5164-567-1. We plot the field lines within a flux tube whose expansion factor is around 6.5 for the section displayed. This value is due both to the latitudinal and longitudinal expansion, which account for about the same expansion rate here. f_{exp} can go up to 10 for thinner flux tubes in the core of the latter, larger one. To quantify the effect of such an expansion on the wind speed, we can use the analytical model brought by Kopp & Holzer (1976) of a polytropic wind solution within an expanding flux tube. From the set of equations:

$$\frac{d}{dr}(\rho v A) = 0, \quad (3)$$

Figure 3: Cut in the (y, z) plane of an expanding flux tube in the TYC 65164-567-1 solution. The color background represents the Mach number on the same scale than Figure 1. The sonic surface is represented in blue and the field lines of the selected flux tube are represented in black. We can see the latitudinal superradial expansion caused by the collimation and the dead zones structure. The expansion factor between the sonic point and a $15R_{\star}$ sphere is about 6.5.

$$\rho v \frac{dv}{dr} + \frac{dp}{dr} + \frac{GM_{\star}}{r^2} \rho = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{d}{dr}(p/\rho^{\gamma}) = 0, \quad (5)$$

where $A(r)$ is the section of the flux tube, one can obtain a

single first-order differential equation on the Mach number $M = v/\sqrt{\gamma p/\rho}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1 - 1/M^2}{2 + (\gamma - 1)M^2} \frac{dM^2}{dr} &= \left[\frac{1}{A} \frac{dA}{dr} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\gamma + 1}{\gamma - 1} \right) \frac{GM_\star}{r} \right], \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\gamma + 1}{\gamma - 1} \right) \frac{1}{g} \frac{dg}{dr}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where

$$g(r) = A(r)^{2(\gamma-1)/(\gamma+1)} \left(E + \frac{GM_\star}{r} \right), \quad (7)$$

and $E = (1/2)v^2 + \gamma p/(\rho(\gamma - 1)) - GM_\star/r$ is the energy of the wind. It can be seen from equation (6) that the local behavior of the Mach number is controlled by the balance between the evolution of A and the gravitational term, which is represented by $(1/g)dg/dr$. The wind accelerates when dg/dr and $1 - 1/M^2$ have the same sign and decelerates when they are of opposite sign¹.

In the spherically symmetric case, *i.e.* the classical Parker polytropic wind solution where $A \propto r^2$, dg/dr is negative when the wind is subsonic and positive when the wind is supersonic (and is thus zero at the critical radius as required by equation (6)). Consequently, the wind always accelerates below and beyond the critical point. When a subradial or a superradial expansion is added, the wind behavior can be modified. The expansion factor can be conveniently parametrized as (Kopp & Holzer, 1976):

$$f_{\text{exp}} = \frac{f_{\text{max}} e^{(r-r_{\text{exp}})/\sigma} + [1 - (f_{\text{max}} - 1)e^{(r_\odot - r_{\text{exp}})/\sigma}]}{e^{(r-r_{\text{exp}})/\sigma} + 1}, \quad (8)$$

where r_{exp} is the radius where most of the expansion occurs, σ quantifies the spatial distribution of the expansion and f_{max} stands for the total expansion at infinity. We will focus here on superradial expansion, *i.e.* $f_{\text{max}} > 1$.

Figure 4: Profil of dg/dr for different f_{max} and r_{exp} . Below the critical radius r_c of the strictly radial solution, the superradial expansion can make dg/dr change sign.

¹We always have $\gamma > 1$.

In Figure 4, we show how the term dg/dr is modified by the expansion factor. We plot four different amplitudes for the expansion ($f_{\text{max}} = \{1.0, 3.5, 6.5, 10\}$, corresponding to the value observed in our simulations) taking place at two different locations ($r_{\text{exp}} = \{1.5, 8.5\}$). We can see that dg/dr can change sign below the usual critical point r_c of the strictly radial case $f_{\text{max}} = 1$. Hence, the wind will be accelerated and decelerated during the expansion.

When the expansion takes place beyond the critical point, dg/dr is already positive and the superradial expansion can only make the wind accelerates more than the radial solution. The solutions can be obtained using an integral form of equation (6) and a model for the expansion (see Kopp & Holzer, 1976). We recover these behaviors in the Mach profile of the wind solutions for a temperature corresponding to the case of TYC 5164-567-1 displayed in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Wind solutions for equation (6) for different expansion parameters. In the upper panel, the expansion occurs mostly around $r_{\text{exp}} = 1.5r_\odot$, and the value of the expansion factor changes drastically the shape of the solution, creating a new critical point for $f_{\text{max}} = 10$. In the lower panel, the expansion only changes the amplitude of the Mach number and is not responsible for any deceleration.

In the upper panel, we vary the amplitude of the expansion f_{max} that occurs below the sonic surface ($r_{\text{exp}} = 1.5r_\odot$). We observe that compared to the spherically symmetric case in

blue, the superradial expansion makes the wind solution accelerate and decelerate. Moreover, for the largest expansion ($f_{\max} = 10$), the wind goes through a new critical point located closer to the star². The effect of the expansion on the terminal speed is only significant for the largest expansion factor.

In the lower panel of Figure 5, the expansion takes place beyond the sonic point and we observe a systematic acceleration of the outflow. Here, the terminal speed is strongly modified even for rather small superradial expansions. f_{\max} controls the amplitude of the acceleration and for the maximum case $f_{\max} = 10$, the Mach number is increased by 70 % and reach 3.2 at $10r_{\odot}$. The mach number obtained through this expansion is coherent with the value found in figure 1 and 3 where the highest value is ~ 3.5 , in the case of TYC 5164-567-1. The magneto-centrifugal effect is not taken into account in this model and is likely to be responsible for the remaining acceleration in our simulations.

4 Discussion

In this study, we demonstrate that the combination of high rotation and complex, intense magnetic fields is able to create a new acceleration process of young stars' winds. This effect rely on the superradial expansion of flux tubes in the supersonic regime, which is due to two factors. The latitudinal expansion is due to the collimation of field lines toward the axis while the longitudinal expansion is due to the strong magnetic flux concentration of the observed fields used in our study. This longitudinal modulation of the magnetic field is to be expected given the existence of active longitude (Berdyugina, 2005). This effect is fundamentally different from the magneto-centrifugal acceleration, which has been extensively studied, although both are probably combined to create the fastest wind of our study.

The analytical model used here (Kopp & Holzer, 1976) confirms that the expansion observed in the simulations is coherent with the speed increase. Hence, strong, realistic magnetic fields and high rotation are likely to create a third component in the wind speed distribution that has no equivalent in the solar wind. Indeed, the first two peaks of our young stars' wind speed distributions can be identified as the slow and fast solar wind component through their correlation with the structure of the coronal magnetic field. The slowest component is correlated with the dead zone edges and the current sheet structure while the intermediate component comes from coronal holes. The amplitude of the peaks might, however, be shifted to higher values using more physical heating mechanisms such as Alfvén waves turbulence processes (Suzuki & Inutsuka, 2006; Oran *et al.*, 2013; Sokolov *et al.*, 2013; van der Holst *et al.*, 2014).

This study also shows the limits of potential extrapolation from the surface field for young stars' coronae. For instance, the potential field source surface model (Schatten *et al.*, 1969; Altschuler & Newkirk, 1969), is not able to describe the influence of high rotation on the field lines, and this kind of model cannot be used as a reliable proxy to compute the expansion factor for young stars, as it assumes that the field becomes purely radial more or less beyond the sonic surface (see for more details Réville *et al.*, 2015b).

²Actually two other critical points are created, an X-type and a O-type in addition to the usual X-type critical point of the Parker solution (see Kopp & Holzer, 1976).

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